

LEGAL REGULATING OF GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES TO ESTABLISH SOUND REGIONAL GOVERNMENT-OWNED ENTERPRISES (PERSERODA)

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Abstract

This research is motivated by The condition is that Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) are businesses owned by the Regional Government, whose purpose is to serve as a source of regional revenue (PAD). However, in reality, existing BUMDs have not been able to make a significant contribution to regional original revenue (PAD). The existence of BUMDs so far, especially regional limited companies (Perseroda), is unlike State-Owned Enterprises, most of whose business activities already apply the principles of good corporate governance (GCG). This research aims to answer the problem regarding the regulation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles in Perseroda according to Indonesian positive law, the implementation of the regulation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles in Perseroda in Indonesia, as well as the model of regulation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles in the future in realizing a healthy Perseroda. This research is a normative legal research using the Statute Approach, Conceptual Approach and Analytical Approach methods. The results of the study indicate that the Regulation of GCG principles in Indonesia regulated in Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government experiences a lack of clarity or ambiguity in its normative implementation in the management of BUMD at the regional level, thus causing problems, such as transparency and accountability. The model of regulating GCG principles in the future in realizing a healthy BUMD is a regulatory model based on systemic and comprehensive principles. The suggestions that the author can provide from this research are To strengthen the management of BUMD in regional government, normative institutions are needed that balance the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders to provide legal protection and certainty and reduce the potential for conflict between profit-seeking and compliance with applicable regulations.

Keywords: Good Corporate Governance, GCG, Perseroda, BUMD.

INTRODUCTION

Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) are businesses owned by the regional government, intended to serve as a source of regional revenue (PAD). However, the reality is that existing BUMDs have not been able to make a significant contribution to regional original revenue (PAD). Instead, they receive more cash injections from the regional government than profits. This situation places a burden on the regional budget (APBD). Consequently, the purpose of establishing BUMDs, which is to serve as a source of regional government revenue, is not being achieved. (Muryanto & Djuwityastuti, 2014)

The existence of Regionally-Owned Enterprises so far, especially regional limited companies (Perseroda) is not like State-Owned Enterprises, most of whose business activities have implemented the principles of good corporate governance or in accordance with the principles

of good corporate governance (hereinafter referred to as GCG) as outlined in the Decree of the Minister of State-Owned Enterprises Number Kep-103/MBU/2002 concerning the establishment of an audit committee for State-Owned Enterprises. The condition of State-Owned Enterprises is one step ahead compared to the business activities carried out by Regionally-Owned Enterprises, and even state-owned enterprises in the form of limited companies have stepped into becoming public companies by issuing their shares on the stock exchange. (Muryanto & Djuwityastuti, 2014)

Furthermore, normative constraints include diversity in the objectives, parameters, and scope of GCG principles. At the national level, Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government stipulates that Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) aim to provide public benefits by providing quality goods and services to meet the needs of the community.

In this context, GCG implementation places greater emphasis on corporate social responsibility and the public interest, which must be tailored to the characteristics and potential of the region. This objective focuses on achieving broad benefits for the community, which is the primary basis for implementing GCG in BUMD.

In contrast, Law No. 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies, although there is no explicit obligation regarding the implementation of GCG, this regulation emphasizes the importance of the principles of good faith, propriety, and good governance as the basis for company operations.

This indicates that at the limited liability company level, the implementation of GCG focuses more on the internal aspects of the company, namely on morality, integrity, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. The application of GCG principles in this context aims to ensure that decisions taken by management are always based on ethical values and fairness.

On the other hand, regulations issued by the Financial Services Authority (OJK), such as OJK Regulation No. 30/PJOK-05/2014 and OJK Regulation No. 10/POJK-05/2022, regulate the implementation of GCG principles by emphasizing the importance of transparency and accountability at every level of a company's organization, particularly in the financing and IT-based funding services sectors. Here, GCG serves as a tool to ensure that every company decision prioritizes not only profit but also compliance with transparent standards and efficient management.

The implication in the context of regional regulations is that GCG principles are considered optional, not imperative. Although these principles are included, their implementation depends on the Board of Directors. Therefore, while GCG principles are generally similar, their implementation in Indonesia varies, tailored to the objectives of each sector, local conditions, and regional characteristics.

This demonstrates that GCG is not merely a universal standard, but also a principle that must be adapted to achieve sustainability, fairness, and effectiveness in the management of regional limited liability companies that are responsible and oriented towards public benefit.

In the context of implementing Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principles in Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD), there are a number of issues that can be viewed from various philosophical, legal, theoretical, and sociological perspectives. Philosophically, the main issue relates to the balance between public objectives and private interests in the implementation of GCG. On the one hand, BUMD aims to provide public benefits by providing goods and services to the community, while on the other hand, the implementation of GCG in private companies is more focused on morality, integrity, and internal company compliance. This raises the question of how GCG can balance these two aspects, ensuring that management decisions prioritize ethical values and justice without neglecting the social benefits that are the main objective of BUMD.

Legal issues arise from the diversity of GCG regulations across various types of companies. Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government emphasizes that regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD) must prioritize public benefit, but does not explicitly mandate the implementation of GCG. Meanwhile, Law No. 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies, although emphasizing the principles of good faith and good governance, does not explicitly mandate the implementation of GCG. This creates legal uncertainty regarding how GCG principles should be implemented, both at the regional level and in private companies. Meanwhile, regulations issued by the Financial Services Authority (OJK) emphasize the importance of transparency and accountability in the financing sector, but also create potential overlap with other applicable regulations.

From a theoretical perspective, the application of GCG in the context of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD) and limited liability companies (PTs) presents challenges in integrating the concepts of good governance theory with the realities of company operations. This raises questions about the extent to which GCG principles, generally considered universal standards, can be effectively and relevantly applied to address challenges at the regional level and in accordance with local characteristics.

Sociological issues relate to the social impact of GCG implementation, particularly regarding public trust in the management of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD). When GCG is implemented in a more flexible or optional manner, there is a risk of declining public trust in the principles of transparency and accountability, which in turn can reduce trust in the management of public companies. Furthermore, local social and cultural characteristics also influence how GCG principles are accepted and implemented, and whether they are sufficient to ensure the achievement of desired social sustainability goals.

Furthermore, Indonesia's weak law enforcement makes the principle of good corporate governance a necessity to protect the interests of all parties. The application of good corporate governance principles is an absolute requirement for companies to achieve good performance in the corporate sector, which will ultimately have a domino effect on improving the global economy. However, this condition contrasts with the concept of good corporate governance, which is applied optionally in Indonesia.

By implementing good corporate governance principles, it is hoped that the interests of all parties involved in the company will be protected without compromising the rights of shareholders, even minority shareholders. Thus, the implementation of good corporate governance will reduce conflicts or disputes among all parties involved in a corporation, including shareholders, stakeholders, and the government in general.

In this regard, the model of good corporate governance (GCG) regulation in the future in realizing a healthy Perseroda is very urgent, considering the chaotic law enforcement in Indonesia amidst the absence of laws and regulations that accommodate business interests, causing the implementation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles to be an absolute requirement for all companies, including Perseroda without exception. Based on the description of the problem, this study will examine the regulation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles in Perseroda according to Indonesian positive law, the implementation of good corporate governance (GCG) principles in Perseroda in Indonesia, as well as the model of good corporate governance (GCG) principles regulation in the future in realizing a healthy Perseroda.

RESEARCH METHODS

Because legal research is a process of discovering legal rules, legal principles, and legal doctrines to address the legal issues faced, the type of research chosen is normative legal research related to the Nature of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) to Create a Professional Limited Liability Company (Perseroa). (Marzuki, 2010) To address the problem in this research, the approaches used include the Legislative Approach, the Conceptual Approach, and the Analytical Approach. (Marzuki, 2010) The legal materials in this research consist of Primary Legal Materials, Secondary Legal Materials, and Tertiary Legal Materials. The legal material collection technique that supports and relates to the presentation of this research is document study (literature study). conducted using content analysis. (Butarbutar, 2018) The legal materials collected and obtained in the research were analyzed using comparative techniques by comparing one opinion with another. These opinions were identified in a quantity deemed sufficient to provide clarity on the legal material being compared. (Diantha, 2016)

DISCUSSION

1) Regulation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) Principles in Limited Liability Companies According to Indonesian Positive Law

In relation to the existence of regional limited liability companies (hereinafter abbreviated as perseroda), they are one of the economic actors in the national economic system, in addition to private business entities and cooperatives. (Jafar, 2016) The role of regional limited liability companies in the national economic system is to produce goods and/or services needed to realize community prosperity and are a significant source of regional revenue. Although at the implementation level, the existence of regional limited liability companies is unique, varied, and difficult to compete with. (Yulianto, 2000)

Various studies indicate that regional limited companies are not managed well because regional limited companies do not yet have a corporate culture that impacts the company's vision and mission.

The management of regional limited liability companies (LLCs) does not conform to sound business management principles or is based on good corporate governance principles, resulting in local government interference in company operations. Local government intervention is considered immune from criticism, resulting in the management of regional limited liability companies tending to be unprofitable and uncompetitive. Consequently, company management demonstrates an unpreparedness to face the ever-changing business environment. (Tuifiq, 2015)

In this context, the position of the Regional Head in a Limited Liability Company (Perseroda) is crucial because, as the majority shareholder, he influences key decisions at the General Meeting of Shareholders (GMS), including capital management, board appointments, and other strategic decisions. Therefore, it is crucial to properly implement GCG principles, including transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, and fairness.

The application of good corporate governance principles to company management has become a normative and legal obligation. (Nuryan, 2016) However, this only applies to banking, capital markets, and state-owned enterprises. Among others:

- a. Law Number 17 of 2003 concerning State Finances Related to the Concept of State Assets was ratified.

Although the GCG principle is categorically emphasized in this provision, on the one hand it has sparked controversy, related to the concept of state assets being separated in capital participation in government-owned business entities (BUMN and BUMD) starting from a misleading understanding and giving rise to its own legal problems when there are two laws that interpret the concept of state finance and company finance (BUMN) in conflicting and diametrically opposite ways. (Atmadja, 2010)

This diametric can be seen in the provisions of Article 2 letters g and i of Law Number 17 of 2003 concerning State Finance that: 1). State/Regional assets managed independently or by other parties in the form of money, securities, receivables, goods, and other rights that can be valued in money, including assets separated in State/Regional Companies; and 2). assets of other parties obtained by using facilities provided by the government.

- b. Law Number 25 of 2007 concerning Investment

Specifically regarding good corporate governance, it is regulated in Article 15 letter a of Law Number 25 of 2007 which states, "Every investor is obliged to: implement the principles of good corporate governance; carry out corporate social responsibility; make reports on investment activities and submit them to the Investment Coordinating Board; respect the cultural traditions of the community around the location of the investment business activity; and comply with all provisions of laws and regulations."

c. Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies

Although in Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies there is no provision that expressly requires companies to implement good corporate governance, the regulation of good corporate governance is explained in the explanation of Article 4 of Law Number 40 of 2007 which states: "the enactment of this law, the Company's articles of association, and the provisions of other laws and regulations, does not reduce the obligation of every Company to comply with the principles of good faith, the principle of propriety, the principle of propriety, and the principles of good corporate governance in running the Company. What is meant by "provisions of other laws and regulations" are all laws and regulations related to the existence and operation of the Company, including their implementing regulations, including banking regulations, insurance regulations, financial institution regulations. In the event of a conflict between the articles of association and this law, this law shall prevail."

d. Government Regulation Number 54 of 2017 concerning Regionally-Owned Enterprises

In this Regulation, the regulation of good corporate governance is contained in Article 7 concerning the establishment of a Regionally-Owned Enterprise (BUMD) which aims to: provide benefits for the development of the Regional economy; provide public benefits in the form of providing quality goods and/or services to fulfill the needs of the community according to the conditions, characteristics and potential of the Region concerned based on good corporate governance; and obtain profits and/or benefits.

e. Regulation of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) of the Republic of Indonesia Number 30/PJOK-05/2014 concerning Good Corporate Governance for Financing Companies

Article 2 paragraph (1) of Chapter II, which regulates the Implementation of Good Corporate Governance, emphasizes that every company is obliged to implement the principles of good corporate governance in all its business activities. This obligation applies at all levels or levels of the organization, without exception. Thus, this article emphasizes the importance of implementing transparent, accountable, responsible, independent, and fair governance as the foundation of company operations, which covers all lines of the organization to ensure efficiency, competitiveness, and contribution to the sustainability of the company and the economy as a whole.

f. Regulation of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10/POJK-05/2022 concerning Information Technology-Based Joint Funding Services

Provisions regarding good corporate governance are regulated in Chapter VIII, part one, concerning governance principles. The obligation to implement the principles of good corporate governance (GCG) in all business activities is mandatory. This obligation covers all levels of the organization without exception. This provision aims to ensure that all company operational activities are managed professionally, transparently, accountably, responsibly, and fairly, thereby creating trust, efficiency, and business sustainability, as well as making a positive contribution to stakeholders and the business environment as a whole.

g. Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government

Article 343 of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government stipulates that BUMD Management must at least fulfill the following elements: procedures for capital participation; organs and personnel; evaluation procedures; good corporate governance; planning, reporting, development, supervision; cooperation; use of profits; assignments by the Regional Government; loans; internal supervisory units, audit committees and other committees; health level assessment, restructuring, privatization; changes in legal form; bankruptcy; and mergers, amalgamations and takeovers.

Based on the above legal provisions, specifically related to BUMD, which in the context of its management is part of the regime of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. Departing from this Law, namely in Article 4. Therefore, with both a teleological and systematic interpretation approach, the meaning of the Provisions in Article 4 can be understood as not only confirming legal certainty but also confirming the principle of legal hierarchy in the management of the Company. The Law is the highest legal norm that must be complied with by all Companies in Indonesia.

Furthermore, the articles of association serve as "household rules" that detail the Company's internal governance, but must still comply with the Limited Liability Company Law. Finally, the Company is also required to comply with applicable sectoral regulations and government policies.

Thus, Article 4 stipulates that all Company activities, both operational and strategic decision-making, must be conducted in accordance with applicable law. This aims to create legal certainty, transparency, and accountability in the Company's management, while also protecting the various parties interacting with the Company.

Compliance with laws and regulations, the application of high moral values, and social responsibility inherent in legal principles are the main foundations for managing Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD). This foundation ensures that corporate governance is oriented not only toward economic efficiency but also upholds ethical values and sustainability. These principles provide a solid foundation for achieving the broader goal of optimizing company performance to support regional development.

Accordingly, the implementation of good corporate governance principles is aimed at ensuring the achievement of the company's goal of increasing local revenue. This success depends on the company's ability to create optimal work value, enabling it to compete effectively at both the regional and national levels.

The principles of good corporate governance encourage the organs of regional public limited companies to act professionally, efficiently, and effectively. The application of good corporate governance principles serves as a guideline for corporate organs to make decisions and carry out actions based on high moral values and compliance with laws and regulations. (Fransiska, 2022)

According to Nuryani, the role of regional government in managing regional limited companies is based on the principles of good corporate governance, namely:

- 1) In the Fairness Principle, as the majority shareholder, the local government can provide protection for minority shareholders. The role of the local government according to this principle is to make clear regulations so that all company assets are managed well and prudently, so that they can provide protection for the interests of shareholders honestly and fairly. The principle of fairness is the soul to monitor and guarantee fair treatment among various interests in the company;
- 2) In the Transparency Principle, to realize the principle of transparency, the role of the regional government is through the General Meeting of Shareholders to ensure the availability of sufficient, accurate, and timely information to various parties interested in the regional limited liability company. This way, stakeholders can be aware of potential risks and enable efficiency in company management.
- 3) Under the Accountability Principle, the role of local governments is to establish independent and credible audit committees to ensure effective internal audits and the company's achievement of its objectives. Implementing this principle will provide clarity on the functions, rights, obligations, authorities, and responsibilities of shareholders, the board of commissioners, and the board of directors.
- 4) Under the Responsibility Principle, the role of local governments is to monitor and evaluate whether company management complies with laws and regulations and sound corporate principles. These regulations cover taxation, industrial relations, environmental protection, occupational health/safety, wage standards, and fair competition. (Nuryan, 2016)

So, in its position as a shareholder, the regional government has great authority to implement the principles of good corporate governance in the management of regional limited companies.

As explained by Darmawati, the regional government's authority as the majority shareholder, in accordance with the essence of good corporate governance principles, is to improve company performance by monitoring management performance. The regional government's role is to oversee, monitor, and evaluate the implementation of good corporate governance principles within the company, particularly for directors, commissioners, and employees. (Darmawati, 2003)

1. Implementation Principles of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in Limited Liability Companies in Indonesia

Based on a study conducted by researchers on regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD) in Indonesia, researchers identified several factors as to why BUMDs consistently experience losses, namely: BUMDs lack regulations governing BUMDs; BUMDs lack GCG guidelines; BUMDs are unprofessional; and BUMDs do not utilize their competitive advantages. (Amdanata & Mansor, 2017)

The four factors that contributed to regional-owned enterprise (BUMD) consistently incurring losses were reduced to three after the government issued Government Regulation No. 54 of 2017 concerning BUMD. Article 92 of this regulation addresses Good Corporate Governance, and the governance referred to here refers to the General Guidelines for GCG in Indonesia, issued by the National Committee for the Assessment and Application of Technology (KNKG) in 2006.

In fact, the existence of this article also reduces the factors that cause BUMD to suffer losses, however, the GCG guidelines are still general in nature, so BUMD needs to identify and assess what kind of GCG is appropriate for the BUMD, (Amdanata & Mansor, 2016) this is because each company requires different governance from one another. (Bruton, Ahlstrom & Wan, 2001)

Research conducted by Donal Devi Amdanata shows that 35%, or 20, of the BUMDs that meet all criteria. Meanwhile, 39%, or 22, of the BUMDs that do not meet all criteria. The remaining 26%, or 15, are BUMDs that only meet one or two criteria. This fact confirms the research findings, which show that BUMDs in Indonesia are still not transparent in presenting financial data, as evidenced by only 20 BUMDs committing to informing the public about their BUMD financial reports. (Amdanata, 2019)

The lack of transparency in these regional-owned enterprises (BUMDs) ultimately creates distrust within the community. This distrust is ultimately channeled to the people's representatives in the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD), making it understandable that the DPRD is consistently harsh in its reprimands of BUMDs. This situation is certainly not good for the BUMDs themselves.

Furthermore, based on research by Baiq Nanda Refina Githary Putri, et al., the case of the West Sumbawa Regional Public Company (Perusda) Board of Directors serves as a clear example of a violation of good governance principles. The directors' actions in disobeying legal provisions, including ignoring the approval of the Regent and the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) before entering into a partnership, resulted in state losses and a violation of criminal law in the form of corruption. This resulted in severe penalties, including imprisonment and the obligation to compensate for losses. This case emphasizes the importance of integrity, transparency, and compliance with regulations in the management of a Regionally-Owned Enterprise (BUMD) to prevent detrimental actions that could potentially undermine public trust in government institutions. (Putri, 2024)

Besides West Sumbawa Regional Public Company (Perusda), the poor management of state-owned enterprises (Perseroda) can be seen in the management of PT Patut Patuh Patju in West Lombok Regency. PT Patut Patuh Patju's profit and loss statements for 2023 and 2024 show a worsening trend of losses, despite significant revenue increases. (Annual Report, 2024)

This situation indicates serious issues in corporate governance, particularly in terms of cost efficiency, budget accountability, and strategic decision-making. The imbalance between increasing revenue and soaring expenses, particularly in the non-productive sector, reflects weak internal controls and non-performance-oriented management. If these companies receive

regional budget (APBD) injections, recurring losses will become a burden on regional finances without a commensurate contribution to Regional Original Income (PAD) or economic benefits for the community. This situation reinforces the urgency of implementing Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principles as a foundation for healthy management of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD).

The implementation of GCG principles such as transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, and fairness is crucial to improving the governance of PT Patut Patuh Patju. Without transparency in budgeting and financial accountability, it is difficult to assess whether the company's spending reflects strategic needs or is simply structured waste.

By adopting a comprehensive GCG-based regulatory and management model, the company will have a more disciplined framework for controlling costs, setting strategic priorities, and holding its performance accountable to the public and local government. Without serious improvements oriented toward GCG principles, PT Patut Patuh Patju will not only continue to post losses but also become an example of failed regionally-owned enterprise (BUMD) management, which is detrimental to regional finances and undermines public trust.

The implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principles in the management of Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) often depends on the policies of the Board of Directors. In this context, the implementation of GCG principles becomes optional, not imperative. This reflects the weakness in the regulations related to BUMD which do not provide specific directions and guidelines as found in State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) which have a legal umbrella through Law Number 19 of 2003. In accordance with Article 3 Paragraph (1) of the Limited Liability Company (PT) Law, the responsibility of the parent company towards its subsidiaries is limited to the capital invested in the subsidiary.

In the legal relationship between a parent company and its subsidiaries, there are minority rights representing the shareholder group of the subsidiary with a portion of shares not owned by the parent company. These minority rights are particularly relevant in the regional context, as they represent the majority shareholder in a subsidiary of a regionally-owned enterprise (BUMD).

Minority shareholders are in a weaker position compared to majority shareholders. Therefore, the state is obliged to pay more attention to minority shareholders, both in protecting their personal rights when dealing with company organs, as well as in safeguarding the interests of the company itself. (Sjawie, 2013) Although the parent company and subsidiaries are combined in a group company construction, the legal status of each is still recognized independently. The parent company as the majority shareholder has limited liability amounting to the value of the shares entered against the inability of the subsidiary to fulfill its legal responsibilities to third parties.

The research results show that the ambiguity in the legal form of Perseroda occurs due to the unclear regulation of the Perseroda's legal status, which lies between the public and private legal domains. This ambiguity causes Perseroda to be unable to function independently as a business entity in the form of a Limited Liability Company. Therefore, the restructuring of Perseroda's legal status aims to transform public management and control to be in accordance

with the principles of private management, as stipulated in the Limited Liability Company Law, and based on the Principles of Good Corporate Management.

Non-compliance with the implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principles in the management of a Regionally-Owned Enterprise (Perseroda) has a significant impact on various important aspects of the performance and image of Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD).

In this context, the main problems that arise are lack of transparency and low accountability, which in turn reduces the level of public trust in the Perseroda. This not only impacts the reputation of the BUMD in the eyes of the public, but also reduces the Perseroda's contribution to Regional Original Income (PAD), which is the main purpose of establishing a BUMD.

Non-compliance with GCG principles also has the potential to cause state financial losses due to inefficient and unaccountable management. From a managerial theory perspective, this condition can be analyzed through various perspectives, such as Shareholder theory and Stakeholder theory, as well as other relevant theories such as Stewardship theory and Agency theory.

Within the framework of shareholder theory, the primary objective of managing a Perseroda (locally-owned enterprise) is to maximize profits for shareholders, which in this case is the local government. Failure to adhere to GCG principles leads to management inefficiencies, which hinder the Perseroda's contribution to local revenue (PAD), thus reducing the economic benefits that should be enjoyed by the community.

In contrast, Stakeholder Theory broadens this focus to include various parties with a stake in Perseroda's operations, such as the community, employees, and other stakeholders. Failure to comply with GCG principles harms all these stakeholders, both directly through reduced economic benefits and indirectly through diminished public trust in local governments and public institutions in general.

Stewardship theory, which emphasizes the importance of a trusting relationship between management and owners, also suggests that this non-compliance reflects a failure of managers to carry out their responsibilities as "stewards" who should focus on long-term interests and positive contributions to PAD.

Finally, agency theory identifies potential conflicts of interest between managers as agents and local governments as principals. Failure to adhere to GCG principles, in this case, could reflect abuse of authority or inefficient management, which is detrimental to the state and society.

Overall, non-compliance with GCG implementation in the management of regional state-owned enterprises (Perseroda) has had widespread and detrimental impacts, both financially and socially, and in terms of reputation. Therefore, strategic steps are needed to improve Perseroda management, including increased oversight, transparency, and accountability, to maximize the contribution of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD) to regional development and avoid state losses.

2. Model Arrangement Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in the Future to Realize a Healthy Regional Company

The economic challenges facing regions are increasingly complex, particularly related to the role of Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) as entities owned and managed by the Regional Government. As business entities, BUMDs play a highly strategic role in driving regional economic development. Their existence is believed to have a significant impact on the local economy, as BUMDs not only create new jobs but also stimulate productive economic sectors and stimulate regional economic growth.

However, one of the main challenges in the management and development of BUMD is the legal aspects that govern them. Current regulations do not provide clear direction and guidelines in the management of BUMD as is the case with State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) which already have a clear legal umbrella, namely Law Number 19 of 2003. Regulations regarding BUMD, which are largely based on Regional Regulations (Perda) and Law Number 5 of 1962 concerning Regional Companies, are deemed not to fully accommodate the need for more modern and optimal management.

In this regard, a Good Corporate Governance (GCG) model is needed in the future to realize a healthy state-owned company, namely a "regulatory model based on systemic and comprehensive principles", which not only regulates organizational structure and governance, but also instills cultural values of accountability and transparency, and prioritizes maximum benefits for the community.

Good GCG arrangements must be adaptive and dynamic, able to accommodate social, economic, and political developments, and create legal certainty for all parties involved, while still considering the welfare of society as a whole.

As for the arrangements in question in the form of regional regulations which regulate Perseroda as a model for realizing a healthy Perseroda containing the following material:

No	Aspect	Description
1	Good Corporate Governance (GCG)	It regulates the principles that must be applied in the management of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD), such as transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, and fairness. The implementation of GCG aims to improve company performance and strengthen public trust.
2	General Policy Regarding Regionally-Owned Enterprises	Policy arrangements that cover the role and contribution of BUMD in regional development, including long-term goals, strategies, and visions that must be aligned with regional development policies.
3	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) of Regionally-Owned Enterprises	Establish clear and measurable operational procedures in carrying out BUMD business activities, including financial management, human resources, and other operations.
4	BUMD Organs	The organizational structure of a BUMD must be designed to be efficient and effective in carrying out its duties and responsibilities.
5	Capital Owner/Shareholder	Explains the rights and obligations of shareholders (local government) in managing BUMD, including in terms of supervision and strategic decision-making by complying with the

		Principles of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) which in the implementation of the GMS must include a discussion on the implementation of GCG principles as a priority agenda.
6	Supervisory Board/Board of Commissioners	The role of the supervisory board or commissioners in overseeing the operational running of BUMD and providing advice to the directors to improve company performance.
7	Board of Directors	Regulates the management of the company by the board of directors, including the authority, duties and responsibilities in carrying out BUMD operations.
8	Determination of Income for Directors and Supervisory Board/Board of Commissioners of BUMD and its Subsidiaries	Regulate the mechanism for determining income for directors and commissioners which must be in accordance with company performance and applicable regulations.
9	BUMD employees	Regulates the recruitment, training, development and management of BUMD employees to ensure the quality of competent human resources.
10	Assignment to BUMD	Regarding the assignment of regional government to BUMD to carry out certain projects or programs related to public services or the regional economy.
11	BUMD Health Level Assessment	Regulations regarding the evaluation of the performance and financial condition of BUMD to ensure that the company remains in a healthy condition financially and operationally.
12	Technical Implementation of GMS / Annual Meeting / Shareholder Approval / KPM Approval	Procedures for implementing the General Meeting of Shareholders (GMS) or annual meeting to make strategic decisions related to the management of BUMD.
13	Use of Profit	Regulations regarding how BUMD profits are used, both for reinvestment in the company, as a contribution to Regional Original Income (PAD), and other distributions in accordance with established policies.
14	Fixed Assets and Inventory	Management of fixed assets and inventory owned by BUMD, including maintenance, transfer and supervision of these assets.
15	Organizational Structure and Work Procedures	Regulations regarding effective organizational structures and clear work procedures in order to facilitate BUMD operations.
16	Cooperation	Regulates various forms of cooperation that BUMD can undertake with other parties, both the private sector and BUMN, which can provide strategic benefits for the company.
17	Restructuring	Regulations regarding the BUMD restructuring process, whether in the form of internal reorganization, changes in capital structure, or other changes to improve company performance.
18	Responsibility and Claims for Compensation	A regionally-owned enterprise (BUMD) is responsible for losses arising from negligence or unlawful actions. Compensation claims can be filed if management fails to comply with regulations or causes harm to other parties.
19	Guidance and Supervision	Coaching is provided to provide direction and training, while supervision ensures that the regional-owned enterprise (BUMD) complies with GCG regulations and principles. This supervision can be carried out by the Supervisory Board or a related institution.
20	Principles of Regionally-	Implementation of the principles of transparency, accountability,

	Owned Enterprise Governance	responsibility, independence, and fairness to ensure good and effective management to support regional economic development.
21	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) of Regionally-Owned Enterprises	SOPs cover important aspects such as organizational structure, staffing, finance, customer service, business risks, asset management, procurement of goods and services, supervision, and others.
22	BUMD Organization	Consisting of various organs that have different duties and authorities in regional public companies (PUD) and regional limited companies (PPD).

The solutions proposed in this text have strong relevance to address various philosophical, legal, theoretical and sociological issues that arise in the management of Perseroda with the application of GCG principles.

First From a philosophical perspective, the tension between public objectives and private interests, benefit and legal certainty, arises. Efforts to clarify company regulations and involve stakeholders in ongoing training and development will help find a balance between public and private interests.

Properly enforced GCG principles will maximize benefits for society while providing legal certainty for all relevant parties. More systematic and detailed regulation in binding regulations will ensure that public goals, such as improving community welfare and contributing to regional development, can be achieved without sacrificing legitimate private interests.

Second, from a legal perspective, GCG regulations are scattered across various regulations and experience a lack of clarity. One of the main solutions proposed is the formulation of more detailed and comprehensive regulations regarding the application of GCG principles in Perseroda.

The formulation of clear and predictable regulations will reduce the current lack of clarity in norms, thus providing stronger and more certain guidelines for actors in Perseroda. With firmer regulations, the implementation of GCG principles is expected to be more focused and minimize misinterpretations or abuse of authority.

Third, from a theoretical perspective, there is a problem between universal principles and the operational reality of the Company. The solutions proposed in the text, such as strengthening internal and external supervision, as well as the application of technology in Perseroda management, aim to bridge the gap between universal GCG principles and the operational reality faced by the company. While GCG principles are well-founded in theory, practical implementation often presents challenges. Therefore, by strengthening oversight structures and leveraging technology to enhance transparency and accountability, universal GCG principles can be more effectively operationalized in the context of a state-owned enterprise (Perseroda).

Fourth, from the sociological aspect of the conflict between universal principles and social sustainability. The implementation of a systemic and comprehensive GCG model also contributes to social sustainability by prioritizing transparency, accountability, and management oriented toward community welfare.

By strengthening training for managers and introducing a culture of integrity, Perseroda will be better prepared to face the challenges of achieving long-term social goals, which include increasing contributions to local revenue (PAD) and overall community welfare. Well-implemented GCG principles play a crucial role in ensuring broader social sustainability, which aligns with regional development goals and the public interest.

Overall, the proposed solution is highly relevant in addressing the philosophical, legal, theoretical, and sociological issues faced by Perseroda in implementing GCG principles. The implementation of clearer policies, strengthened oversight, and the adoption of efficient technology are expected to support the achievement of a balance between public and private interests, as well as the realization of a healthier, more transparent, and more accountable Perseroda organization.

The epistemological approach applied in the management of BUMD, particularly in the clear and detailed application of GCG principles, is highly relevant and coherent with the axiological dimension of BUMD. From an epistemological perspective, the development of more comprehensive regulations on GCG reflects the process of creating valid and legitimate knowledge, which focuses not only on legal aspects but also on the moral values underlying company management. GCG principles such as transparency, accountability, and social justice form the foundation of knowledge that BUMD managers need to understand well, so that the policies implemented are not only legally valid but also support community welfare and the public interest.

Furthermore, strengthening internal and external oversight, as well as utilizing technology to increase transparency, plays a role in reinforcing desired axiological values, such as integrity and accountability. The use of technology for efficiency and transparency also supports the broader implementation of GCG principles, in line with moral values that prioritize social sustainability. In this regard, the establishment of GCG principles in the Articles of Association and Bylaws (AD/ART) of a Perseroda is a crucial step in ensuring that GCG principles are consistently implemented and recognized as an inherent obligation within the organizational structure.

This establishment ensures that all Perseroda managers, including directors and commissioners, are legally bound to comply with these principles in every strategic and operational decision they make. Thus, the AD/ART serves not only as an internal legal basis but also as a moral and ethical guideline that leads to fair and transparent management, and is oriented towards public welfare.

Furthermore, ongoing training and coaching for Perseroda managers is also an important step in ensuring management that is not only based on proper legal knowledge, but also on high ethical values, such as social responsibility and integrity.

Thus, the epistemological approach that emphasizes legitimate, transparent, and accountable management closely coheres with the axiological objectives of BUMD, namely to create a positive impact on society and support sustainable regional development.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

- a) The regulation of GCG principles is spread across several laws and regulations in positive law in Indonesia, namely Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies (PT Law), Law Number 19 of 2003 concerning State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN Law), Law Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets, Law Number 21 of 2011 concerning the Financial Services Authority (OJK), Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government experiencing unclear GCG regulations which have an impact on the lack of clarity or ambiguity in its normative implementation in the management of BUMD at the regional level;
- b) The implementation of GCG principles has not been carried out properly. This has led to issues such as transparency and accountability, which have resulted in a decline in public trust and a diminished image of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMDs), resulting in minimal contributions to local revenue (PAD), and resulting in state financial losses.
- c) The future Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principle regulatory model in realizing a healthy BUMD is a regulatory model based on systemic and comprehensive principles, which not only regulates organizational structure and governance, but also instills cultural values of accountability and transparency, and prioritizes maximum benefits for the community.

2. Suggestions

To strengthen the management of Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) within the regional government, a normative body is needed that balances the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders to provide legal protection and certainty and reduce potential conflicts between profit-seeking and compliance with applicable regulations.

Clearer regulations are needed to regulate the legal status of BUMDs, so that they can function independently and transparently in accordance with the principles of good management.

Furthermore, to strengthen the application of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) principles in BUMD management by implementing a merit system model, by reconstructing Article 39 and adjusting the phrase "regionally owned" in Article 30 of Government Regulation No. 54 of 2017.

This strengthening emphasizes that the selection of appointments is the authority of shareholders and prevents nepotism in BUMD management.

In addition, a sunset clause based on performance evaluation with a 10-year time limit needs to be applied to BUMDs that do not contribute to Regional Original Income (PAD). All of these models serve as normative references in the formation of BUMDs through Regional Regulations.

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